

A STUDY OF EUROPEAN IDENTITY BUILDUP

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Introduction:

In 2005, the people of France and the Netherlands defined the initial predictions of a vast majority of analysts by voting against a proposal to create a Constitution for Europe. Others concluded that European citizens simply demonstrated an 'obvious' lack of European identity, unprecedented levels of Euroskepticism, or a general sense that integration has gone far beyond what the public wished, preferring a 'technical' and economic integration (Bruter, 2008, p273). In this case, what is the European identity? Due to accelerating of Euroskepticism, several national elections from Denmark, Italy, Austria, France and The Netherlands are confirming the strength of populism and the far-right party which impose its speech in the public debate, which is at the heart of economic, cultural and identity protectionism (Chopin, 2016). To intensify European power, European identity should be reinforced and ensured more. The purpose of this study is considering who can be European people? How does European identity create? The first chapter describes the definition of European and European identity by referring to some scholars. The second chapter presents how the creation of European identity and its identification. In the last chapter, it will be considered which instruments are used to establish and intensify European identity.

The Definition of European Identity:

As the first step in this analysis, it will be examined what the European identity is and who can be European. Where Europe is, there is not an agreement, and just divided with continents cannot tell. Christianity has been thinking an essential factor to create a European identity. The founders of the EU's Christian Democratic Party, mostly faithful Catholics, saw themselves in Christian or Carolingian symbology as 'national identity constructors'. Moreover, the Vatican and the Catholic hierarchies provided the "uniting of Europe" in this same period (Nelsen, & Guth, 2016). However, current Europe has had other influences, such as the French revolution and the separation between religion and politics. Therefore debate is sterile and demagogical, because the root of Europe is Christianity, but not the only one (Troitino, 2013). Identity is not just shaped the behaviour of individuals, but also significant potential cooperation among groups and societies. A shared identity in groups promotes confidence and cooperation (La Barbera and Ferrara, 2012). As a critical driver in the emergence of a nation state, a kind of European identity is seen as a prerequisite for the European Union's stable life and further development (Ciaglia, Fuest, & Heinemann, 2018, p8). Cram (2012) mentioned defining European identity is identification as European and, it is essential to distinguish between three key categories to understand the role played by identity in the European integration process: identification as European, identification with European, support for EU. To understand what is European identity genuinely, next chapter will address to consider in respect of the identification as European.

The Identification of European Identity:

Does European imply the people who support the EU? Even though the citizens of Europe support for the EU, it is not necessary they consider themselves as European. As a good example, Cram (2012) provided the case of the United Kingdom and Ireland. This research conducted Eurobarometer, which asked regarding the responsibility for the EU support or not. The answers to these questions in the United Kingdom are consistently in the two Member States at the bottom, whereas the Irish answers always are in the top three. However, when asked whether the Irish and British respondents identified as more or less European, the EU average of EU identifiers is both below that. They retain their national identity, but still appreciate the opportunities for EU cooperation (Fligstein, 2008). Identification of European identity is normalised by identification with European. In European citizens, identification is primarily based on low - level dailies involving the European Union in unusual widespread ways such as carriage of passports or driving licenses, compliance with law and, passing EU flags. Reminding citizens whether for good or worse they are involved in the broader EU systems (Cram.2001). Meanwhile, the European identity has been created within the lives and imaginings of citizens. Europe has great diversity, with a population of over 750 million people and nearly 500 million in the EU, over 200 languages, over 2,000 dialects, various ethnic groups, numerous national groups (Troitino, 2013). Therefore, it is not only difficult to clearly distinguish a European identity from national identity but also using the concept of collective European identity leads to many risks (Holesch, 2013). Troitino (2013) distinguished "national identity is more 'cultural', while European identity that is more 'instrumental'." In the following chapter, it will examine what kind of European "identity building" tools are used.

Instrumental of European Identity Building:

How does European identity build? What kind of instrumental has been used?

Holesch (2013) stated five “European identity building tools”- which are Education and language, European citizenship and mobility, Communication sphere – media, Invented traditions/Symbolism, and Common EU myth. He mentioned that these significant elements were to create a European identity. Here, it will focus on the three points, education and languages, European citizenship and mobility and, communication.

In the Maastricht Treaty, it showed “the Community shall contribute to the development of quality education by encouraging cooperation between the Member States.” It depicted that EU education should have become an essential tool for intensifying identity in Europe. The European Commission hoped that the Erasmus program, which is the most popular bilateral or multilateral exchange programs among higher education students, will develop a robust European identity and the Erasmus generation will be created (Shore, 2000). As languages, in the European Union there are three principal working languages (English, French and, to a certain extent, German);

‘Do you speak a second language?’	No	Yes
Overall	38.4	61.6
By country:		
Luxembourg	2.3	97.7
Denmark	12.6	87.4
Sweden	12.6	87.4
Netherlands	13.0	87.0
Finland	28.8	71.2
Belgium	37.6	62.4
Germany	41.3	58.7
Italy	44.7	55.3
Ireland	46.6	53.4
Greece	46.8	53.2
France	47.0	53.0
Spain	52.3	47.7
Austria	52.7	47.3
Portugal	53.5	46.5
Great Britain	64.3	35.7

Table 1: the countries use of second languages (European Commission, 2012)

However, the EU works in the context of 23 official and six half-official languages in particular. The EU officially promotes multilingualism and attempts to encourage EU citizens to speak, in addition to their mother tongue, two foreign languages at least (Holesch, 2013). However, the level/ use of second language skill tends to vary depends on the size of the country and the languages are used in Europe. The second language usage is unevenly distributed across countries, according to Table 1. Citizens residing in smaller EU countries like Luxembourg and the Netherlands are much more likely than people living in larger countries to speak a second language. People also speak a second language in the Scandinavian countries of Finland, Sweden and Denmark. In any country except Austria, Portugal, Spain and Great Britain, the majority of the population claim to speak a second language. English speaks a second language the least, with 64,3% speaking English alone (Fligstein, 2008, p153).

As European citizenship and mobility, Baubock (2007) defined the European citizens as “a nested membership in a multilevel polity that operates at member state and union levels”, which includes two primary components: supranational democratic representation that expressed by EU citizen’s right to vote in European Parliament or local elections in foreign countries, or internal free movement, related to the right to live or work in each Member State of the EU. This internal free movement by European citizenship is one of the important elements to develop a European identity. There are two different ways to be mobile. First, the highly-educated European elite. Second, searching for employment in other countries. Members of both groups can be considered as ambitious individuals, who historically have always left their country in the search for a better life (Holesch, 2013). As a question, who can be the European citizen? The answer is straightforward. "Every person holding the nationality of a Member State shall be a citizen of the European Union." In other words, if you are not an EU Member State citizen, people cannot be a European Union citizen (Holesch, 2013). It means that if European citizens do not live in another Member State, they do not experience any benefits and thus have a residual impact on their integration (Troitino, 2013).

These two elements motioned above were already implemented and to some extent effect on the European identity. Considering communication such as media, it is one of the possible tools to intensify the European identity. Media for the creation of European identity is entirely counterproductive (Holesch, 2013). The European Commission was aware that information is essential - “Information is a decisive, perhaps the most decisive, factor in European unification. However, the EU has no European media of its own. At the same time, it also has in its back a national media that protects the nation-state and challenges any "identity

building" in Europe. It makes it hard to integrate Europe more, while there is an exception. The movement of European media has been increasing, such as the European news channel "Euro news" and some newspapers like the EU observer that is "Brussels - centred" and are distributed only in cities of EU institutions (Holesch, 2013). Also, the Eurovision channel, the Ryder Cup, the United States - European golf competition or European football events (Troitino, 2013) also impact on the establishment of European identity.

Conclusion:

To resisting the crisis of the EU due to the lack of European identity, European identity is needed to reinforce and clarify what the European identity is. The key to the European identity is secure and stable life and future development of the European Union. On the account, European identity defined identification as European by Cram (2012), considered identification as European would develop the European identity. However, it does not mean that those who support for EU have a European identity. European identity is standardised by European identification. In other words, European identity was created by instrumental methods on the dairy level in Europe with diversity national culture and difference. As the tools to establish the identity, this paper focused on three points, which are education and languages, European citizenship and mobility and, communication. The people who can get these benefits such as free mobility to work and educate are only those who have citizenship of EU member states. Therefore, European citizen is naturally identified as European, and also communication tools such as media will help to develop European identification more. The European identity - building process has only just started, and forces are growing over time to produce more collective European identity (Fligstein, 2008, p157). However, this paper has still problematic and contradiction regarding emerging Euroscepticism regardless of the benefits to be European. As the expectation of its reason, the gap of benefits between the EU countries would be argued. I consider that future research is to examine more insight into European situation and response for the European between the member-states, or between elites and workers.

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